

Taxonomic review of Indian species of the genus *Ceranisus* Walker (Chalcidoidea: Eulophidae)

*Mohd Majid Jamali¹, Shahid Bin Zeya² & Rayees Afzal Mir¹

¹Department of Agriculture, Glocal University, Saharanpur 247 121, Uttar Pradesh, India.

²Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh 202 002, Uttar Pradesh, India.

(Email: majidjamali1988@gmail.com)

Abstract

The Indian species of *Ceranisus* Walker (Eulophidae: Entedoninae) are reviewed. The review includes four species, of which *C. udnamtak* Triapitsyn is recorded for the first time from India. Male is described for the *Ceranisus udnamtak* Triapitsyn for the first time from the world.

Keywords: Hymenoptera; Entedoninae; parasitoid; new record.

Received: 24 January 2019; Revised: 31 December 2019; Online: 31 December 2019

Introduction

The species of genus *Ceranisus* Walker are considered as an important parasitoids, attacking the larval stage of thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) (Schauff, 1991; Loomans, 2003; Triapitsyn, 2005). These are potential agents in the bio-control of thrips pests of economically important plants. Presently this genus contains 40 species from the world, of which only 3 species are known from India (Noyes, 2019).

In this paper, we record 4 species, of which *C. udnamtak* Triapitsyn, is a new record from India. All species are fully diagnosed and thoroughly illustrated and an identification key to Indian species is also provided.

Materials and Methods

The present study is based on a small collection of entedonine parasitoids (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae: Entedoninae) collected from the Indian states of Andhra Pradesh, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh mainly by sweep net, otherwise noted under the section of material examined section. The body colour was noted from card mounted specimens before clearing and mounting the specimens on slides in canada balsam. Body length for the new species is given in millimetres. All other measurements are relative taken from the divisions of a linear scale of a micrometer placed in the eye piece of a compound microscope. These measurements were taken at 100×

magnification of the microscope. The photographs of card mounted specimens were taken with digital camera (Nikon DS-Fi2) attached to a stereozoom (Nikon SMZ25) and the photographs of slide mounted parts were taken with a digital camera (Nikon DS-Fi1c) attached to a compound microscope (Nikon Eclipse Ci).

The following abbreviations are used in the text:

C1, C2 etc.: Clava segments 1, 2 etc.

F1, F2, etc.: Funicle segments 1, 2 etc.

(MT): Malaise Trap. This abbreviation is used in brackets under 'Material examined section, to indicate the method of collection.

T1, T2, etc.: Gastral tergites 1, 2 etc.

The following acronyms are used for the depositories:

CAS: California Academy Sciences, San Francisco, California, USA.

QMB: Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia.

ZDAMU: Insect collections, Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India.

Systematics accounts

Genus *Ceranisus* Walker

(Figures 1–27)

Ceranisus Walker, 1842, [Explanation of plates A-P (illustrations of genera of Chalcidoidea by Haliday).] Entomologist 1(26): Plate N, Fig. 2.

Type species *Cirrospilus pacuvius* Walker, by monotypy.

Thripoctenus Crawford, 1911: 233. Type species *Thripoctenus russelli* Crawford, by monotypy. Synonymy by Graham 1959: 203. Stat. Rev., by Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 457,497. Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2015: 1.

Epomphale Girault, 1915: 211. Type species *Epomphale auriventris* Girault, by original designation. Synonymy by Bouček 1988: 733. Stat. Rev., by Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 457, 495. Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2015: 1.

Urfacus Doğanlar, 2003: 182. Type species *Urfacus bozovaensis* Doğanlar, by monotypy and original designation. Synonymy by Doğanlar & Triapitsyn, 2007: 105. Stat. Rev. by Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 489. Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2015: 4.

Gaziantepus Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 457, 491. Type species *Gaziantepus oguzeliensis* O. Doğanlar, by monotypy and original designation. Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2015: 1, 4.

Sergueicus Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 457, 502. Type species *Ceranisus barsoomensis* Triapitsyn, by monotypy and original designation. Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2015: 1, 4.

Guelsenia Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 457, 499. Type species *Ceranisus amanosus* Doğanlar, Gumovsky and O. Doğanlar, by original designation. Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2015: 1, 4.

Diagnosis: Female: Head dark brown to black. Antenna yellowish brown. Mesosoma dark brown to black; Fore wing subhyaline, venation brown; hind wing largely hyaline. Legs pale yellow to pale brown. Gaster pale yellow to pale brown. Head with occipital suture may be straight, sinuate or angulate; frontal groove reaching eyes on level of anterior ocellus; mandible reduced, without teeth. Antenna (13, 21) with funicle 2-segmented and clava 2- or 3-segmented; last claval segment with a long spicula. Mesosoma usually smooth, mesoscutum anteriorly with incomplete notaular lines; mid lobe of mesoscutum with 4 or 5 setae (except 1 pair in most *C. russelli* (Crawford) (Triapitsyn, 2005). Metasoma with petiole at most broader than long.

Male: Similar to female except sexual dimorphism and clava 3-segmented, last claval segment with long spicula (Figs 19, 26).

Hosts: Endoparasitoid of thrips larvae (Bouček, 1988; Schauff, 1991).

Distribution: Worldwide

Species: World: 40; India: 4

Comments: Taxonomic history of *Ceranisus* was given in detail by Doğanlar & Doğanlar (2013).

Key to Indian species of *Ceranisus* Walker, females

1. Antennal clava 3-segmented (Fig. 2); mid lobe of mesoscutum with 2 setae
.....*C. javae* (Girault)
- Antennal clava 2-segmented; mid lobe of mesoscutum with 4 or 5 (at least 3 specimens of *C. menes*) setae 2
2. Fore wing disc either without bare area or a narrow bare area present along posterior margin behind base of marginal vein, it is demarcated anteriorly by a more or less straight cubital line of setae (Fig. 9).....*C. femoratus* (Gahan)
- Forewing disc with a distinct semi-oval bare area at posterior margin behind base of marginal vein, demarcated anteriorly by a sinuate line of setae (Figs. 16, 23)..... 3
3. F1 a little shorter or subequal to F2 (Fig. 13); postmarginal vein of fore wing shorter than stigmal vein (Fig. 16)*C. menes* (Walker)
- F1 a little longer than F2 (Fig. 21); postmarginal vein of fore wing distinctly longer than stigmal vein (Fig. 23)*C. udnamtak* Triapitsyn

1. *Ceranisus javae* (Girault)

(Figures 1–5)

Epomphale javae Girault, 1917: 1, female. Lectotype, female, Indonesia, Java, Salatiga (USNM), not examined.

Thripoctenus maculatus Waterston, 1930: 243, male, female. Syntype, male, female, Pakistan, Layalpur (BMNH). Synonymy by Husain & Khan, 1986: 212.

Thripobius semiluteus Bouček, 1976: 412, female. Holotype, female, Africa, Sao

Tomé (BMNH). Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2005: 310.

Ceraninus maculatus (Waterston): Loomans & van Lenteren, 1995: 128, diagnosis, biology.

Thripobius semiluteus Bouček: Bouček, 1988: 734, diagnosis, record. Loomans & van Lenteren, 1995: 132–137, diagnosis, biology.

Ceraninus javae (Girault): Loomans & van Lenteren, 1995: 132, diagnosis.

Thripobius javae (Girault): Triapitsyn, 2005: 310.

Redescription:

Female: Length, 0.56–0.59 mm. Head brown with reddish reflection, eye reddish. Antenna with scape pale yellow, pedicel and flagellum pale yellow with brownish tinge. Mesosoma brown except pronotum dark brown. Wings hyaline and setose apically. Legs, including coxae pale white to pale yellow. Gaster pale yellow.

Head (Fig. 1) in frontal view, 1.41–1.6× as broad as high; eye height 2.10–2.66× as long as malar space. Antenna (Fig. 2) with scape 5.14–6.33× as long as broad, 2–2.11× as long as pedicel; pedicel 2–2.25× as long as broad; F1 almost rectangular, longer than F2 with one sensillum; clava 3-segmented, 2.28–3.16× as long as broad.

Mesosoma (Fig. 3) almost smooth; pronotum narrow, hardly visible in dorsal view; mesoscutum subequal to scutellum; notauli incomplete, distinct anteriorly; mid lobe of mesoscutum medially with a pair of setae; scutellum sub-rectangular with 1+1 setae near latero-posterior angle; each side lobe of mesoscutum and axilla with one seta. Fore wing (Fig. 4) 2.83–3× as long as broad; marginal vein+parastigma 1.34–1.52× as long as submarginal vein; disc setose; longest marginal seta 0.53–0.63× maximum wing width. Hind wing (Fig. 5) 10.25–10.5× as long as broad; longest marginal seta 2–2.25× as long as maximum wing width.

Metasoma shorter than mesosoma; petiole 3× as broad as long; ovipositor not exerted beyond apex of gaster and 0.66–0.84× as long as hind tibia.

Relative measurements (n=3): Head height: width, 12–12.5: 17–20; eye height, 8–9; malar space, 3–4.5. Antennal segments—length: width; scape, 9–9.5: 1.5–1.75; pedicel, 4.5: 2–2.25; F1, 1.75–2.25: 2; F2, 1.25–1.5: 2–2.5;

C1, 2.25–3: 3–3.5; C2, 2.5: 3–3.5. Mesosoma length, 21–24. Forewing length: width, 41–46: 15–16; marginal vein length, 13.5–16; submarginal vein length, 11.5–12.5; parastigma length, 2–3; post marginal vein length, 1–1.5; stigmal vein length, 2–3; longest marginal seta, 8–9.5. Hind wing length: width, 41–42: 4; longest marginal seta, 8–9. Hind tibia length, 13–15. Metasoma- Petiole length: width, 1–3; gaster length, 17–19; ovipositor, 10–11.

Male: Unknown.

Material examined: INDIA: UTTARAKHAND: Dehradun, Sahaspur, 3 females (on slide, slide. Nos. EUL.102 and EUL.103, EUL.125), 19.iii.2016, Coll. M.M. Jamali & P.T. Anwar (ZDAMU).

Distribution: India: Karnataka, Punjab & Uttarakhand (**new record**).

Figures 1–5. *Ceraninus javae* (Girault) Female: **1.** head, frontal view; **2.** antenna; **3.** mesosoma; **4.** fore wing; **5.** hind wing.

Comments: *Ceraninus javae* (Girault) comes close to *C. russelli* (Crawford) in having 3-segmented clava, but differs in following characters: antenna with F1 distinctly longer than F2; fore wing with submarginal vein shorter than marginal vein; postmarginal vein

shorter than stigmal vein. In *C. russelli* antenna with F1 subequal or shorter than F2; fore wing with submarginal vein longer than marginal vein; postmarginal vein longer than stigmal vein.

2. *Ceranisus femoratus* (Gahan)

(Figures 6–11)

Thripoctenus femoratus Gahan, 1932: 747, female. Holotype, female, Philippines, Luzon, Laguna (USNM), not examined.

Ceranisus femoratus (Gahan): Baltazar, 1966: 112. Loomans & van Lenteren, 1995: 130, 196, diagnosis; 196, synonymy. Triapitsyn, 2005: 299, diagnosis; 300, illustration.

Redescription:

Female: Length, 0.78 mm. Head dark brown to black. Antenna with scape and pedicel brown, flagellum pale brown; mesosoma dark brown to black. Fore wing subhyaline; hind wing largely hyaline. Legs with coxae and femora brown to dark brown except trochanter of mid leg pale white, tibiae pale brown, tarsi pale white. Gaster brown.

Head (Fig. 6) in frontal view, 1.44× as broad as high. Antennal (Fig. 7) scape 4.2× as long as broad, 2.2× as long as pedicel; pedicel 1.9× as long as broad; funicle 2-segmented; F1 subequal to F2, both with one placoid sensilla; clava 2-segmented, 1.5× as long as broad.

Mesosoma (Fig. 8) almost smooth; pronotum narrow, visible in dorsal view; mesoscutum slightly shorter than scutellum; notauli incomplete; mid lobe of mesoscutum with 4 setae; each side lobe at posterior angle with 1 seta; scutellum slightly broader than long with 1 seta at each lateral margins. Fore wing (Fig. 9) 2.3× as long as broad; marginal vein+parastigma 1.6× as long as submarginal vein, 7.8× as long as stigmal vein; post marginal vein 1.3× as long as stigmal vein; longest marginal seta 0.23× maximum wing width. Hind wing (Fig. 10) 6.5× as long as broad; longest marginal seta 0.81× as long as maximum wing width.

Metasoma (Fig. 11) longer than mesosoma; petiole 1.7× as broad as long; ovipositor occupying three-fourth of gaster length, slightly exerted beyond the apex of gaster; ovipositor 1.87× as long as hind tibia.

Relative measurements: Head height: width, 18: 26. Antennal segments–length: width; scape, 10.5: 2.5; pedicel, 4.75: 2.5; F1, 3: 2.25;

F2, 3: 2.5; clava, 6.75: 4.5. Mesosoma length, 32. Fore wing length: width, 56: 24; submarginal vein length, 14; parastigma length, 2; marginal vein length, 21.5; post marginal vein length, 4; stigmal vein length, 3; longest marginal seta, 5.75. Hind wing length: width, 52: 8; longest marginal seta, 6.5. Hind tibia length, 16. Metasoma- Petiole length: width, 2.5: 4.25; gaster length, 35; ovipositor, 30.

Male: Unknown.

Material examined: INDIA: ANDHRA PRADESH: Vishakhapatnam, Rajipeta, 1 female (on slide under four coverslips, slide No. EUL.211), 3.ii.2014, Coll. M.T. Khan. (ZDAMU).

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh.

Figures 6–11. *Ceranisus femoratus* (Gahan) Female: **6.** head, frontal view; **7.** antenna; **8.** mesosoma; **9.** fore wing; **10.** hind wing; **11.** metasoma.

Comments: The redescription of the species is based on material collected from Indian state of Andhra Pradesh agreeing fairly well with the redescription given by Triapitsyn (2005). However *C. femoratus* comes close to *C.*

votetoda Triapitsyn (2005), but differs in following characters: antenna with funicle segment F1 subequal to F2, each with one sensillum; mesosoma with moderate pronotum; fore wing with longest marginal setae almost one-fourth maximum wing width; hind wing 6.5× as long as broad; longest marginal seta distinctly shorter than maximum wing width. In *C. votetoda*: antenna with funicle segment F1 distinctly shorter than F2 and F1 and F2 without sensillum; mesosoma with a long pronotum; fore wing with longest marginal setae almost one-tenth maximum wing width; hind wing 8× as long as broad; longest marginal seta equal to maximum wing width.

3. *Ceranisis menes* (Walker)

(Figures 12–20)

Pteroptrix menes Walker, 1839: 18, female. Lectotype, female, England, London (BMNH), not examined.

Thripoctenus brui Vuillet, 1914: 553, female. Paratype, female, France (USNM). Synonymy by Bouček, 1961: 26.

Thripoctenus vinctus Gahan, 1932: 746, female. Holotype, female, Philippine, Luzon, Laguna (USNM). Synonymy by Triapitsyn, 2005: 293.

Ceranisis rosilloi De Santis, 1961: 13, female. Holotype, female, Argentina (MLP). Synonymy by De Santis & Fidalgo, 1994: 89.

Euderomphale menes (Walker): Erdős, 1956: 25.

Ceranisis menes (Walker): Graham, 1959: 203. Bouček, 1961: 26, record. Graham, 1963: 203, catalogue. Bouček & Askew, 1968: 137, record. Trjapitzin, 1978: 426, record. Bouček, 1988: 734, synonymy, diagnosis. Loomans & van Lenteren, 1995: 99–115, synonymy, diagnosis. Triapitsyn & Headrick, 1995: 233–235, redescription of male and female, host associations, figures. Lacasa, Sánchez & Lorca, 1996: 341–346, 348. Roditakis & Roditakis, 2002: 154, biology. Triapitsyn & Morse, 2005: 72, review. Thangjam *et al.*, 2013: 30, record.

Ceranisis vinctus (Gahan): Baltazar, 1966: 112, catalogue. Loomans & van Lenteren, 1995: 125–127, diagnosis, biology. Bouček & Askew, 1968: 138, synonymy.

Ceranisis brui (Vuillet): Yoshimoto, 1965: 690, record. Murai, 1988: 1–73, biology.

Epomphale menes (Walker): Doğanlar & Doğanlar, 2013: 497.

Redescription:

Female: Length, 0.5–0.85 mm. Head dark brown to black. Antenna pale brown; mesosoma dark brown to black. Fore wing hyaline, venation brown; hind wing largely hyaline. Legs largely pale yellow except coxae in basal half brown. Gaster pale yellow to pale brown.

Head (Fig. 12) broader than mesosoma, in frontal view, 1.23–1.57× as broad as high. Antennal toruli situated below the lower eye margin. Antenna (Fig. 13) with scape 4.4–5× as long as broad, 1.9–2.27× as long as pedicel; pedicel 1.66–2.2× as long as broad; funicle segments slightly longer than broad; F1 subequal or slightly longer than F2; F1 with or without sensillum, F2 with one sensillum; clava 2-segmented, 2.12–3× as long as broad, distinctly longer than funicle, with longitudinal sensilla.

Mesosoma (Figs. 14, 15) 1.18–1.5× as long as broad; pronotum with a pair of thick setae; mesoscutum subequal to scutellum with linolate sculpture; mid lobe of mesoscutum with 4–5 setae; scutellum with 1 setae present in middle near each lateral margins. Fore wing (Fig. 16) 2.5–2.75× as long as broad; marginal vein+parastigma 1.6–1.9× as long as submarginal vein, 5.25–6.42× as long as stigmal vein; post marginal vein short, 0.25–0.5× stigmal vein; longest marginal seta 0.28–0.44× maximum wing width. Hind wing (Fig. 17) 7.6–9× as long as broad; longest marginal seta 1.3–1.5× as long as maximum wing width.

Metasoma distinctly longer than mesosoma; petiole 2–4× as broad as long; ovipositor (Fig. 18) occupying more than two-third length of gaster, slightly exerted beyond apex of gaster; ovipositor 1.2–1.6× as long as hind tibia.

Relative measurements (n=5): Head height: width, 14–21: 22–26. Antennal segments—length: width; scape, 10–12.5: 2–2.5; pedicel, 5–6: 2.5–3; F1, 3–3.5: 2.5; F2, 2.5–3.5: 2.5–3; C1, 3–4.5: 3.5–4.5; C2, 5.5–7.5: 4. Mesosoma length, 26–33: 20–22. Fore wing length: width, 47–64: 17–25; submarginal vein length, 11–15.5; parastigma length, 1.5–2; marginal vein length, 19–26; post marginal vein length,

1–2; stigmal vein length, 3.5–4.5; longest marginal seta, 6.5–9.5. Hind wing length: width, 43–61: 5.5–8; longest marginal seta, 8–11.5. Hind tibia length, 14–20. Metasoma-Gaster length, 33–41; ovipositor, 21–24.

Male: Length, 0.56–0.7 mm, similar in colour to female except sexually dimorphic features. Antenna (Fig. 19) flagellum with long hairs and clava 3-segmented. Genitalia as in figure 20.

Material examined: INDIA: ANDHRA PRADESH: East Godavari, Kokinoda, Thimmapuram, 3 females (on slides, slide Nos. EUL.52, EUL.53 and EUL.54), 7.ii.2014, Coll. M.T. Khan; Guntur, Kulnukonda, 4 females (on slides, slide Nos. EUL.2, EUL.34, EUL.35 and EUL.51), 11.ii.2014, Coll. M.T. Khan; Vishakhapatnam, Rajipeta, 1 male, 3.ii.2014, Coll. M.T. Khan. SIKKIM: Tadong, ICAR campus, 2 males (on cards) 1.xii.2014 (MT), Coll. K. Veenakumari. UTTAR PRADESH: Etah, Patna Pakshihi Vihar (Bird Sanct.), 2 females, 1 male (on slides, slide Nos. EUL.45, EUL.47 and EUL.126), 27.xi.2011, Coll. S.B. Zeya, P.T. Anwar and S.U. Usman. UTTARAKHAND: Roorkee, Delda, 1 female (on slide, slide No. EUL.1), 2.xi.2009, Coll. F.R. Khan; Dehradun, Sahaspur, 2 females (on slides, slide Nos. EUL.116 and EUL.40), 19.iii.2016, Coll. M.M. Jamali and P.T. Anwar (ZDAMU).

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh (**new record**), Karnataka, Sikkim (**new record**), Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand.

Comments: The redescription of the species is based on the specimens collected from several Indian states, agreeing fairly well with the redescription given by Triapitsyn and Headrick (1995) and Thangjam *et al.* (2013). It is to note that all the described species under the genus contain 4 setae on midlobe of mesoscutum but in 3 Indian specimens collected from Andhra Pradesh are with 5 setae. However, it superficially resembles *C. udnamtak* Triapitsyn (2005), but it differs by the characters given under the comments of *C. udnamtak*.

Figures 12–20. *Ceranisus menes* (Walker) (12–18) female: **12.** head, frontal view; **13.** antenna; **14.** mesosoma, showing mid lobe of mesoscutum with 4 setae; **15.** mesosoma, showing mid lobe of mesoscutum with 5 setae; **16.** fore wing; **17.** hind wing; **18.** ovipositor. (19–20) male: **19.** antenna; **20.** genitalia.

4. *Ceranisus udnamtak* Triapitsyn (Figures 21–27)

Ceranisus udnamtak Triapitsyn, 2005, Female. Holotype, female, Nepal, Katmandu (CAS), not examined.

Redescription:

Female: Length, 0.72–0.75 mm. Head metallic dark brown. Antenna with scape pale white; pedicel and flagellum pale brown. Mesosoma metallic dark brown; area around notaular lines and axillae with greenish reflection. Fore wing hyaline. Hind wing largely hyaline. Legs with coxae pale white except hind coxa in basal half brown and tarsi of all legs pale brown. Gaster with T1 and T2 pale white, the remainder pale brown.

Head in frontal view, 1.14–1.25× as broad as high; eye height 2.50–2.63× as long as malar space. Antennal toruli situated at the level of lower eye margin. Antenna (Fig. 21) with scape 5–5.4× as long as broad and 2.5–2.7× as long as pedicel; pedicel 1.67–2× as long as

broad, subequal to F1; F1 slightly longer than F2, each funicle segment with one sensillum; clava 2-segmented, 2.17–2.25× as long as broad.

Mesosoma (Fig. 22) Pronotum smooth, narrow with 4–7 small setae and 2 long setae. Mesoscutum subequal to scutellum, mid lobe of mesoscutum with 2 pairs of setae; each side lobe of mesoscutum with 2 setae; each axilla with one seta; scutellum subquadrate with 1+1 setae near the lateral margins. Fore wing (Fig. 23) 2.32–2.42× as long as broad; marginal vein+parastigma 1.62–1.73× as long as submarginal vein, 5.7–6.5× as long as stigmal vein; post marginal vein very long, 2.11–2.37× as long as stigmal vein; disc more or less uniformly setose; longest marginal seta 0.19–0.22× maximum wing width. Hind wing (Fig. 24) 6.78–7.23× as long as broad; longest marginal seta 1.05–1.12× as long as maximum wing width.

Metasoma slightly longer than mesosoma; petiole 3.2–4× as broad as long; ovipositor not exerted beyond apex of gaster and 1.30–1.34× as long as hind tibia.

Relative measurements (n=3): Head height: width, 20–24: 24–30; eye height, 14.5–15; malar space, 5.5–6. Antennal segments—length: width; scape, 12–13.5: 2.25–2.5; pedicel, 4.75–5: 2.5–3; F1, 4–4.5: 2; F2, 3.5–4: 2–2.5; C1, 3.5–4: 4–4.5; C2, 5.5–6: 4–4.5. Mesosoma length, 32–37. Forewing length: width, 66–72: 28–31; marginal vein length, 23–26; submarginal vein length, 15.5–17; parastigma length, 2–3.5; post marginal vein length, 9.5–10; stigmal vein length, 4.5; longest marginal seta, 5.5–7. Hind wing length: width, 61–65: 9; longest marginal seta, 9.5–10. Hind tibia length, 21–23. Metasoma-Petiole length: width, 1–1.5: 4; gaster length, 31–41; ovipositor, 28–30.

Male: Head (Fig. 25) in frontal view, 1.5× as broad as high; eye height 2× as long as malar space. Antennal toruli situated slightly above the lower eye margin. Antenna (Fig. 26) with scape 3.46× as long as broad, 2.6× as long as pedicel; pedicel 1.6× as long as broad, shorter than F1 and F2 individually; F1 subequal to F2; clava 3-segmented, 3.3× as long as broad.

Mesosoma almost smooth, similar to female. Fore wing 2.28× as long as broad; marginal vein+parastigma 1.7× as long submarginal vein, 5.7–6.5× as long as stigma vein; post

Figures 21–27. *Ceranisus udnamtak* Triapitsyn (21–24) female: **21.** antenna; **22.** mesosoma; **23.** fore wing; **24.** hind wing. (25–27) male: **25.** head, frontal view; **26.** antenna; **27.** genitalia.

marginal vein 2.3× as long as stigmal vein; longest marginal seta 0.23× maximum wing width. Hind wing 6.84× as long as broad; longest marginal seta subequal to maximum wing width.

Metasoma slightly longer than mesosoma; petiole 2× as broad as long. Genitalia as in figure 27.

Relative measurements: Head height: width, 19: 29; eye height, 13; malar space, 6. Antennal segments length: width; scape, 13: 3.75; pedicel, 5: 3; F1, 6.5: 3.25; F2, 6.75: 3.5; C1, 5: 4; C2, 5: 4.5; C3, 4.5: 3.25. Mesosoma length, 41. Forewing length: width, 73: 32; marginal vein length, 26; submarginal vein length, 17; parastigma length, 3; stigmal vein length, 4.5; post marginal vein length, 10.5; longest marginal seta, 7.5. Hind wing length: width, 65: 9.5; longest marginal seta, 9. Hind tibia length, 23. Metasoma- Petiole length: width, 2.5: 5; gaster length, 46.

Material examined: INDIA: UTTARAKHAND: Sahaspur, Kaichiwala, 3 females, 1 male (on slides, slide Nos. EUL.119, EUL.122 and EUL.123, EUL.228),

19.iii.2016, Coll. M. M. Jamali & P.T. Anwar (ZDAMU).

Distribution: India: Uttarakhand (**new record**); Nepal.

Comments: The redescription of *Ceranisus udnamtak* Triapitsyn is based on the specimens collected from Indian state of Uttarakhand, agreeing fairly well with the original description of *C. udnamtak* given by Triapitsyn (2005). However, it slightly differs from the holotype (characters of holotype, *C. udnamtak* are in parentheses): fore wing 2.32–2.42× as long as broad (fore wing 2.53× as long as broad); longest marginal seta 0.19–0.22× maximum wing width (longest marginal seta 0.25× maximum wing width); pedicel 0.37–0.40× scape length (pedicel 0.43× scape length); ovipositor 1.30–1.34× as long as hind tibia (ovipositor 1.2× as long as hind tibia.). I consider these minor differences fall within the range of variation for the species.

Further it differs from *C. menes* (Walker) in following characters: pedicel subequal or slightly longer than F1; funicle segments distinctly longer than broad; F1 distinctly longer than F2; fore wing with post marginal vein very long, 2.11–2.37× as long as stigmal vein; longest marginal seta 0.19–0.22× maximum wing width. In *C. menes* funicle segments slightly longer than broad; F1 subequal or slightly longer than F2; fore wing with post marginal relatively very short, 0.33× stigmal vein; longest marginal seta 0.35× maximum wing width.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Chairman, Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, for providing research facilities. We also thank Dr. Mohammad Hayat, Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, for constant help and encouragements.

References

Baltazar, C.R. 1966. A catalogue of Philippine Hymenoptera (with a bibliography, 1758–1963). Pacific Insects Monograph 8: 1–488.
 Bouček, Z. 1961. Materials on the chalcid (Chalcidoidea) fauna of the Moldavian SSR. Trudy Moldavskogo Nauchno-

issledovatel'skogo Instituta Sadovodstva, Vinogradarstva i Vinodelia 7: 5–30.

- Bouček, Z. 1976. Taxonomic notes on some Eulophidae [Hym.] of economic interest, mainly from Africa. Entomophaga 21: 401–414.
 Bouček, Z. 1988. Australasian Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera): A biosystematic revision of genera of fourteen families, with a reclassification of species. Wallingford, UK: CAB International Institute of Entomology. 832 pp.
 Bouček, Z., Askew, R.R. 1968. Index of Palaearctic Eulophidae (excl. Tetrastichinae). In: V. Delucchi, & G. Remaudière, (eds.) Index of Entomophagous Insects, 3. Paris: Le François. 9–254 pp.
 Crawford, J.C. 1911. Two new Hymenoptera. Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington 13: 233–234.
 De Santis, L. 1961. Dos nuevos parásitos de tisanopteros de la República Argentina (Hymenoptera: Entodontidae). Notas del Museo, Zoología 20(187): 11–19.
 De Santis, L. and Fidalgo, P. 1994. Catálogo de los Himenópteros Calcidoideos de América al sur de los Estados Unidos. Tercer suplemento (Insecta). Serie de la Academia Nacional de Agronomía y Veterinaria 13: 1–154.
 Doğanlar, M. 2003. A new genus and a new species of Entedontinae (Hymenoptera, Eulophidae) from southeastern Anatolia, Turkey. Turkish Journal of Zoology 27(3): 181–185.
 Doğanlar, M. and Doğanlar, O. 2013. Systematics of the genera with reduced mandible of Eulophidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea): parasitoids of thrips (Thysanoptera). Entomofauna 34(4): 457–516.
 Doğanlar, M. and Triapitsyn, S.V. 2007. Review of *Ceranisus* (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) of Turkey, with description of a new species. European Journal of Entomology 104(1): 105–110.
 Erdős, J. 1956. Additamenta ad cognitionem faunae Chalcidoidarum in Hungaria et regionibus finitimis. VI. Eulophidae. Folia Entomologica Hungarica (Series Nova) 9: 1–64.
 Gahan, A.B. 1932. Miscellaneous descriptions and notes on parasitic Hymenoptera.

- Annals of the Entomological Society of America 25(4): 736–753.
- Girault, A.A. 1915. Australian Hymenoptera Chalcidoidea-IV. Supplement. Memoirs of the Queensland Museum 3: 180–299.
- Girault, A.A. 1917. Notes and descriptions of miscellaneous chalcid-flies (Hymenoptera). Proceedings of the United States National Museum 53(2213): 445–450.
- Girault, A.A., 1934. New Capsidae and Hymenoptera, with note on an unmentionable. Queensland: Private Publication.
- Graham, M.W.R. de V. 1959. Keys to the British genera and species of Elachertinae, Eulophinae, Entedontinae, and Euderinae (Hym., Chalcidoidea). Transactions of the Society for British Entomology 13(10): 169–204.
- Graham, M.W.R. de V. 1963. Additions and corrections to the British list of Eulophidae (Hym., Chalcidoidea), with descriptions of some new species. Transactions of the Society for British Entomology 15(9): 167–275.
- Husain, T. and Khan, M.Y. 1986. Family Eulophidae. In: B.R. Subba Rao and M. Hayat, (eds.) The Chalcidoidea (Insecta: Hymenoptera) of India and the adjacent countries. Part II. Catalogues. Oriental Insects 20: 211–245.
- Lacasa, A., Sánchez, J.A. and Lorca, M. 1996. Aspecto ecologicos de los parasitos de los tisanopteros en Espana. Boletin de Sanidad Vegetal, Plagas 22: 339–349.
- Loomans, A.J.M. 2003. Parasitoids as biological control agents of thrips pests. Thesis, Wageningen University. Wageningen, The Netherlands: Ponsen & Looijen b.v. 200 pp.
- Loomans, A.J.M. and van Lenteren, J.C. 1995. Biological control of thrips pests: a review on thrips parasitoids. In: A.J.M. Loomans, J.C. van Lenteren, M.G. Tommasini, S. Maini, & J. Riudavets. Biological control of thrips pests. Wageningen Agricultural University Papers, 95-1. Wageningen, The Netherlands: Veenman Drukkers. pp. 89–193 + 195–201 (Appendix).
- Murai, T. 1988. Studies on the ecology and control of flower thrips, *Frankliniella intonsa* (Trybom). Bulletin of the Shimane Agricultural Experiment Station 23: 1–73.
- Noyes, J.S. 2019. Universal Chalcidoidea Database. World Wide Web electronic publication. <http://www.nhm.ac.uk/chalcidoidea/> Accessed on 31 December 2019.
- Roditakis, E. and Roditakis, N.E. 2002. Bioecological studies of western flower thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) in vineyards. (Abstract 075) Abstracts, VIIth European Congress of Entomology, Thessaloniki 154 pp.
- Schauff, M.E. 1991. The Holarctic genera of Entedoninae (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae). Contributions of the American Entomological Institute 26(4): 1–109.
- Thangjam, B., Khan, M.A., Pandey, S. and Managanvi, K. 2013. A new species of genus *Pediobius* Walker (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) with new records of eulophid parasitoids from Uttarakhand, India. Pantnagar Journal of Research 11(1): 29–34.
- Triapitsyn, S.V. & Headrick, D.H. 1995. A review of the Nearctic species of the thrips-attacking genus *Ceranisuus* Walker (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae). Transactions of the American Entomological Society 121(4): 227–248.
- Triapitsyn, S.V. 2005. Revision of *Ceranisuus* and the related thrips-attacking entedonine genera (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) of the world. African Invertebrates 46: 261–315.
- Triapitsyn, S.V. and Morse, J.G. 2005. A review of the species of *Ceranisuus* Walker (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) in the New World. Trans. Am. Entomol. Soc. Transactions of the American Entomological Society 131(1+2): 69–86.
- Triapitsyn, S.V. 2015. New records of Eulophidae, Mymaridae, Pteromalidae, and Tetracampidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Russia, with annotations and description of a new species of *Dicopus* Enock. Far Eastern Entomologist 292: 1–12.
- Trjapitzin, V.A. 1978. Subfam. 4. Entedontinae. In: Vol. III, Part 2, Hymenoptera, Trjapitzin, V.A., ed., Skarlato, O.A., Chief ed., Keys to the insects of the European part of the USSR. Leningrad: Nauka, Leningrad division 404–430.

Taxonomic review of Indian species of the genus *Ceranisus* Walker

- Vuillet, A. 1914. Note sur un Chalcidien parasite du Thrips des pois. Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances et Mémoires de la Société de Biologie 76: 552–554.
- Walker, F. 1839. Monographia Chalciditum, Vol. 1. London: H. Bailli'ere.
- Walker, F. 1842, [Explanation of plates A-P (illustrations of genera of Chalcidoidea by Haliday).] Entomologist 1(26): Plate N, Fig. 2.
- Waterston, J. 1930. Two new parasitic Hymenoptera. Annals and Magazine of Natural History 5(10): 243–246.
- Yoshimoto, C.M. 1965. Synopsis of Hawaiian Eulophidae including Aphelininae (Hym.: Chalcidoidea). Pacific Insects 7(4): 665–699.